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Influence of Nārāyaṇīya on Kṛṣṇagīti Dr Jayanisha K¹

Abstract

Nārāyaṇīya of Melputtur Narayana Bhattatiri is the summary of Bhagavata Purana. It is a famous stotra kavya in Sanskrit. Mānaveda, the King of Kozhikode was a contemporary of Melputtur. Mānaveda, an ardent devotee of Kṛṣṇa was influenced by Nārāyaṇīya for its poetical style in his work Kṛṣṇagīti. The story of Kṛṣṇagīti is based on the 10th and 11th Skandha of Bhagavata. Here a comparison is being made on both texts.

Keywords: Melputtur, Nārāyaṇīya, Kṛṣṇagīti, Mānaveda, Kṛṣṇa, Dasaka, Influence, Meter

Nārāyaṇīya of Melputtūr Narayana Bhattatiri is considered to be the summary of *Śrīmad Bhāgavata Purāṇa*. *Bhāgavata* describes the story of the incarnations of Lord Viṣṇu in 12 Skandhas containing 18000 verses. Melputtūr summarised it into 100 Daśakas containing 1033 verses. There are magniloquent passages and verses in *Bhāgavata*, but Melputtūr narrates them lucidly in poetic language with rhythmic words. *Nārāyaṇīya* was acclaimed as a classic from the beginning. There is no wonder that *Nārāyaṇīya* influenced and inspired many writers in writing stories praising lord Kṛṣṇa, both in Sanskrit and Malayalam. Most of these works are well known in Kerala. Among these works *Kṛṣṇagīti* written by Mānaveda stands unique.

Mānaveda, the author of *Kṛṣṇagīti* was the king of Kozhikode. He was born in Nediyruppu dynasty (Warrier 55). He lived from 1584 to 1658 A.D. It is evident from the documents from the archives of Samutiri Palace (Elayad). From the last verse of *Kṛṣṇagīti* we can assume that it was written in 829 of the millennium era

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which is equal to 1653.² He has also written a Campūkāvya called *Purvabharatacampu*.³

Melputtūr died at the age of 86, but he had completed *Nārāyaṇīya* by his 27th age.⁴ So at the time of Mānaveda, *Nārāyaṇīya* had acquired great popularity. Mānaveda was a devotee of Lord Kṛṣṇa and so naturally he was very much influenced by *Nārāyaṇīya*, which contains verses praising Lord Kṛṣṇa. There existed a warm relationship between Melputtūr and Mānaveda. ‘The reasons for this might be Melputtūr’s contact with Samutiri palace, the scholarship and poetic mentality of both of them and their earnest devotion to the Lord of Guruvayur’ (Elayad 37). That is why there is no wonder that Mānaveda’s composition of the verses of Lord Kṛṣṇa resounds *Nārāyaṇīya*. Mānaveda was influenced by *Astapadiyattam* for the stage performance of *Kṛṣṇagīti* and *Nārāyaṇīya* for the poesy.

As mentioned, *Nārāyaṇīya* is considered to be the summary of the entire *Bhāgavata*. But *Kṛṣṇagīti* consists only the 10th and 11th Skandhas of *Bhāgavata*, which describes the events from Kṛṣṇa’s incarnation to his ascension. *Kṛṣṇagīti* gave great prominence to dance and music with act. Though Mānaveda called his work *Kṛṣṇagīti*, it is known as ‘Kṛṣṇanattam’ in Kerala. It is so called because the verses are arranged for the purpose of dance performance. So, it is a kind of visual poem.

Structure and story of Kṛṣṇagīti

The stories mentioned in *Kṛṣṇagīti* can be noticed from 37th to 89th Daśakas of *Nārāyaṇīya*. Mānaveda wrote *Kṛṣṇagīti* in eight sections, which are entitled – Avatara, Kaliyamardana, Rasakrida, Kamsavadha, Svayamvara, Banayuddha, Vividavadha and Svargarohana. Though *Kṛṣṇagīti* is very much influenced by

2. In *Kṛṣṇagīti*, the final part of 24th verse of Svargarohana reads -
ग्राह्याः स्तुतिर्गाथकैः । which denotes the Kalidinas – 1736612 i.e. 829 Kollam era.
3. *Purvabharatacampu* completed in 1644, in eight Stabakas describes the early stories of the lunar dynasty and intended as a supplement to the *Campubhatatam* of Anantabhata.
4. For a detailed discussion of Melputtūr’s age, See, *Contribution of Kerala to Sanskrit Literature*, K. Kunjunni Raja, University of Madras 1980, pp. 130-135.

Nārāyaṇīya, it has included the ascension of Lord Kṛṣṇa which is absent in *Nārāyaṇīya*, but narrated in *Bhāgavata*.

Ksemendra in his *Kavikanthabharana* describes the ambitious poets into four sections namely – Chayopajivi, Padakopajivi, Padopajivi and Sakalopajivi (*Kavikanthabharana*, II. 1). It is evident that Mānaveda was greatly influenced by the Chaya (theme), Pada (word) and Pada (phrases) of *Nārāyaṇīya*, which was popular among the people. However, Mānaveda's poetical identity can be clearly seen in *Kṛṣṇagīti* since he was not a 'Sakalopajivi'. The aforesaid three factors come out from the influence but the fourth one is mere embezzle.

I. Chayopajivitvam

Chaya means congenial quality of ideas. In *Kṛṣṇagīti* one can see many ideas which are described in *Nārāyaṇīya* but not fully mentioned in *Bhāgavata*.

The introductory verses of Avatara are very much akin to the verses of the 37th Daśaka of *Nārāyaṇīya*. Those verses describe mother earth making complaint to Brahma of her grievances. Asuras caused those grievances. Even killed by the Devas, Asuras were not acquitted from their crimes. They were born again. This story is described in *Nārāyaṇīya*, but not mentioned in *Bhāgavata*. However, Mānaveda has adopted the story into his writings.

सान्द्रानन्दतनो हरे ननु पुरा दैवासुरे सङ्गरे
 त्वत्कृत्ता अपि कर्मशेषवशतो ये ते न याता गतिम् ।
 तेषां भूतलजन्मनां दितिभुवां भारेण दूरादिता
 भूमिः प्राप विरिञ्चमाश्रितपदं देवैः पुरैवागतैः ॥ (नारायणीयम् – 37, 1)
 सक्ष्मीनाथ, पुरा सुरासुरमृधे ये कालनेम्यादय-
 स्त्वत्पिष्टावपि श्लिष्टकर्मबलतो दैत्या न मुक्तिं गताः ।
 तेषां भूरिभरेण भूतलजुषां सा भूतधाली व्यथा –
 पात्री वेधसमेत्य वेगत इति प्रोवाच देवावृतम् ॥ (कृष्णगीति – 1. 5)

Thus, from the introductory verses of Avatara itself Mānaveda accepted the idea and style of Melputtūr and expressed his indebtedness to him. It is also notable that in both verses the 'Sardulavikridita' metre is used.

The friends of Kṛṣṇa who had felt resentment, on Kṛṣṇa's

stealing of fruits informed Yasoda that 'Kṛṣṇa had eaten soil'. This portion about stealing of fruits is described in Nārāyaṇīya, which is not present in Bhāgavata. However, Mānaveda accepts this free imagination of Melputtūr. Instead of the word फलसञ्चयवञ्चनक्रुधा (नारा – 46. 2) of Melputtūr, he uses फलकुलसंचोरणात्यन्तकुप्यत् (कृष्ण – 2. 1).

There is a similarity of idea contained in the 2nd verse of Daśaka 62 of Nārāyaṇīya and the 39th verse of Kaliyamardana of Kṛṣṇagīti. The occasion of this narration is the beseech of Nandagopa to Kṛṣṇa for the need of offering to Indra (Indrayaga) and convincing the need of rain on earth.

बभाषे नन्दस्त्वां सुत ननु विधेयो मघवतो
मघो वर्षे वर्षे सुखयति स वर्षेण वृथिवीम् ।
नृणां वर्षायत्तं निखिलमुपजीव्यं महितले
विशेषादस्माकं तृणसलिलजीव्या हि पशवः ॥ (नारा – 62. 2)
जन्तूनां तापशान्त्यै स खलु शतमखः पुष्टिहेतोश्च वृष्टिं
काले काले कृपालुः सृजयति मुदितधीः सर्वलोकैकपालाः ।
वर्षाधीनं नराणां सकलसमुपजीव्यं विशेषादिदं नः ।
सर्वा गव्यापि नव्योपचयमुपजीव्येयमाव्या पृथिव्याम् ॥ (कृष्ण. 2. 29)

Here we can see Kṛṣṇagīti had adopted the idea and phrases of Nārāyaṇīya.

The verses of Rasakrida in Nārāyaṇīya are written in Kusumamanjari metre.

वेणुनादकृततानदानकलगानरागगतियोजना –
लोभनीयमृदुपादपातकृततालमेलनमनोहरम् ।
पाणिसंक्वणितकङ्कणं च मुहुरंसलम्बितकराम्बुजं
श्रोणिबिम्बचलदम्बरं भजत रासकेलिरसडम्बरम् ॥ (नारा – 69. 4)

These verses echo in Kṛṣṇagīti –

पाणिकमलतालमिलितपादपातने ।
पादकटकहेमवलयनादमोहने ॥ (कृष्ण. 6. 1)

These verses are written with rhythmic Pañcari tune and style. Mānaveda has imitated Melputtūr's style of doubling syllables. In the 10th verse of the 81st Daśaka of Nārāyaṇīya Melputtūr describes Kṛṣṇa's theft of Parijata, marrying 16000 damsels and testing Narada:

कल्पद्रुं सत्यभामाभवनभुवि सृजन् द्व्यष्टसाहस्रयथाः
स्वीकृत्य, प्रत्यगारं विहितबहुवपुर्लालयन् केलिभेदैः ।
आश्चर्यान्नारदालोकिविविधगतिस्तत्र तत्रापि गेहे

भूयः सर्वासु कुर्वन् दश दश तनयान् पाहि वातालयेश ॥ (नारा – 81. 10)

The 5th verse of Banayuddha in *Kṛṣṇagīti* also describes the same theme with the same style:

भामारामे निधाय द्युतरुमुदवहोद्व्यष्टसाहस्रनारीः
 प्रीता च प्रत्यगारं विहितबहुवपुर्मोदयामासिथामूः ।
 त्वद्रूपालकनद्यत्कुतुकसुरमुनीन्द्रादिविस्मापकैस्त्वं
 तैस्तैर्लीलाविशेषैः प्रतिनिलयमलं रेजिषे नेमिषे च ॥ (कृष्ण – 6. 5)

II. *Padakopajivitvam*

It was to sustain the meaning of the words of Melputtūr that Mānaveda also used the same terms for describing that occasion. This approach has really enhanced Kṛṣṇagīti. Similar incidents can be seen in many parts of Kṛṣṇagīti. This is very well seen in the occasion when the hermit Garga names Kṛṣṇa:

कथमस्य नाम कुर्वे
 सहस्रनाम्नो ह्यनन्तनाम्नो वा (नारा. 44. 4)
 तेनैवातानयन्नाम स मुसलभृता ते बतानन्तनाम्नः (कृष्ण. 1. 43)

Similarly, this resonance of words is seen in the portion where Yasoda in fury addresses Kṛṣṇa for having eaten soil:

अयि दुर्विनयात्मक त्वया
 किमु मृत्सा बत वत्स भक्षिता । (नारा – 46. 4)
 वत्सेहात्यन्तकुप्यं जगति मृदशनं किं कृतं दुर्विनीत । (कृष्ण – 2. 1)

Kṛṣṇagīti imitated the words like ‘Temanajemana’ which is described in the 51st Daśaka of Nārāyaṇīya: सतेमनार्निरगमदीश जेमनैः । (नारा – 51.1), राजन्तेमनजेमनाः शिशुजनैः साकं भवानेकदा (कृष्ण- 2. 7)

These terms were not used frequently in the antique. But ever since Melputtūr adopted those words they became popular and that may be the reason why Mānaveda also adopted those words. Another example is – अनोपमं ते भवतो निकेतनम् (नारा – 11. 2)

In this line the word ‘Anopama’ which needs scholarship in its explanation. This word is transcribed in Kṛṣṇagīti as it is in Nārāyaṇīya. व्यसनमनोपमममुदितमनूनं (कृष्ण. 1. पदम् 1. 5)

On his way to Mathura Akrura dipped himself in the river of Kalindi and then he saw Lord Kṛṣṇa in the water and also in the chariot. This portion can also be seen in Kṛṣṇagīti as it is in Nārāyaṇīya.

नियमाय निमज्यवारिणि त्वामभिवीक्ष्य रथोपि गान्दिनेयः ॥ (नारा – 73. 7)
 वेगादागाः प्रतीरं दिनकरदुहितुस्तज्जले त्वां विमज्जम् ।
 वीक्ष्योन्मज्ज्यैक्षत त्वामतिकृतुकमपि स्यन्दने गान्दिनेयः (कृष्ण – 4. 19)

III. Padopajivitvam

In Kṛṣṇagīti one can notice the influence of certain verses of Nārāyaṇīya. Kaliyamardana, which indicates the dance steps, is described in 'Totaka' metre. It appears in the 55 Daśaka of Nārāyaṇīya. In the same way Mānaveda mentions four-line poems of third 'Pada' in Kaliyamardana of Kṛṣṇagīti.

भुवनत्रयभारभृतो भवतो (नारा – 55. 3)
 त्रिभुवनभारभृतोजितभवतो (कृष्ण. 2. पदम् 3. 2)

Here one can see how that line of Nārāyaṇīya influenced him. This similarity can be observed in the following verses also:

उदकादुदकादुरगाधिपतिस्तदुपान्तमशान्तरुषान्धमनाः (नारा – 55. 4)
 उदकादुदकादुरगोथरयात् सविधं तव हन्तुमभीतिरयात् (कृष्ण – 2. पदम् 3. 3)

Here one can see besides the words and meaning Mānaveda was influenced by the rhythm of Nārāyaṇīya also.

The third and fourth verses of the 81 Daśaka of Nārāyaṇīya describe the marriages of Kṛṣṇa. These events are seen in the first and second verses of Banayuddha in Kṛṣṇagīti. In this description also there is a similarity of lines but no skid of ideas.

सत्यां गत्वा पुनरुदवहो नग्नजिन्नन्दनां तां
 बध्वा सप्तापि च वृषवरान् सप्तमूर्तिर्निमेषात् । (नारा – 81. 4)
 जित्वा सप्तापि सत्यामहूत वृषवरान् नग्नजिन्नन्दनां ताम् (कृष्ण – 6. 1)

IV. Vrttopajivitvam(Chandopajivitvam)

In addition to Chaya, Pada and Pāda the metrical influence of Nārāyaṇīya is seen in Kṛṣṇagīti. Melputtūr has used about 25 metres. Among them the most important ones are Sragdhara, Sarddulavikriditam, Vasanthatilakam ... etc. Most of them seemed to the latter poets as inevitable to describe those scenes. Melputtūr has used a new metre Kusumamanjari, which is not seen in Vrttaratnakara. The same metre is used by Mānaveda to describe the same event.

The 55 Daśaka of Nārāyaṇīya describes Kaliyamardana in Totaka metre. In the same way Mānaveda mentions the third poem of third

Pada in Kaliyamardana of Kṛṣṇagīti.

अथ दिक्षु विदिक्षु परिक्षुभित
 भ्रमितोदरवारिनिनादभरैः ।
 उदकादुदकादुरगाधिपति-
 स्तदुपान्तमशान्तरुषान्धमनाः (नारा – 55. 4)
 उदकादुदकादुरगोथरयात्
 सविधं तव हन्तुमभीतिरयात् ।
 अपि मर्मसु दुर्मतिरदशदयं
 शिव शिव रभसादपयातभयम् ॥ (कृष्ण – 2. पदम् 3. 3)

Here Mānaveda adopted the style, idea, tune and metre of Nārāyaṇīya. However, it is observed that Mānaveda's भोगनाम्नि नटनमकृत.... gana metre can express more dance effect than totaka metre. The alliteration in the above lines of Kṛṣṇagīti excels more than that of Nārāyaṇīya.

Melputtūr has used Kusumamanjari metre in eleven verses of Rasakrida in Nārāyaṇīya. केशपाशधृतपिञ्छिकाविततिसञ्चलन्मकरकुण्डलं (नारा – 69. 1)

Here importance is given to dance. Kusumamanjari metre is used in Rasakrida of Kṛṣṇagīti also. But it is applied not at the exact occasion of Rasakrida but during the narration of gopikas' coming to Vrṇdavana when they heard fluty sound.

It can be observed that the aforesaid four factors (Chaya, Pada, Pāda and Chandas) of Nārāyaṇīya are resounded in Kṛṣṇagīti.

The assassination of Pancali's children, discussion of the arrow of Brahma (Brahmastra), protection of Uttara's conception.... etc. are narrated in Kṛṣṇagīti with the same effect of word, idea, meaning and style of Nārāyaṇīya.

संसुप्तद्रौपदेयक्षपणहतधियं द्रौणिमेत्य त्वदुक्त्या
 तन्मुक्तं ब्रह्ममस्त्रं समहृतविजयो मौलिरत्नं च जह्नेः ।
 उच्छित्त्यै पाण्डवानां पुनरपि च विशत्युत्तरागर्भमस्त्रे
 रक्षन्नङ्गुष्ठमालः किल जठरमगाश्चक्रपाणिर्भव त्वम् ॥ (नारा – 86. 10)
 संसुप्तद्रौपदीनन्दनहननकरं द्रौणिमेत्यामुनास्त्रं
 ब्रह्मास्त्रं संजहर्त्तुं त्वरितमहूत पार्थश्च तन्मौलिरत्नम् ।
 अस्त्रे सन्तानमन्तं गमयितुमुदरं प्राप्तवत्युत्तराया
 आविष्टाङ्गुष्ठमालं मुरहर तरसा पालयो बालमेतम् ॥ (कृष्ण – 7. 19)

It is notable that in both of the aforesaid set of verses Sragdhara

metre is used.

Thus, in *Kṛṣṇagīti* from beginning to end the influence of *Nārāyaṇīya* is seen in all matters such as diction, word meaning, formation of idea, poetic style, metrical structure, rhyme, style of presentation etc. However, *Kṛṣṇagīti* is not at all an embezzlement of *Nārāyaṇīya*. Mānaveda has taken special care to enlarge the meaning of words and ideas, which he borrowed from *Nārāyaṇīya*. Thus, he was proficient to keep his identity in all the verses in *Kṛṣṇagīti*. Anandavardhana, the author of *Dhvanyaloka* (IV. 11-15) commends that there is no harm in borrowing certain words, phrases or ideas from any original texts of the scholars.

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